

The Greater India Society and Historiography of India

Present-day attempts to saffronise Indian history have a precedent in the Greater India project.

PRATIM DAS

At a book launch event in New Delhi in June 2022, union home minister Amit Shah claimed that Indian historians have remained silent on Hindu empires in their writing and mentioning only the Muslim rulers of the Mughal dynasty. According to Shah, it is high time we (re)wrote “our” history—the “glorious” reigns of dynasties like the Mauryas and the Cholas. The tendency to deny the history of Muslim kings and their empires is not new. Reducing the identity of rulers to their religion, there have been repeated attempts to isolate them and question their Indianness.

Attempting to reconstruct and rewrite India’s history is not a new endeavour. Hindu historians undertook a similar nationalist project almost a hundred years ago to write Indian history through a new lens. Determined to rewrite the history of India, an organisation called the Greater India Society was founded in Calcutta in 1926 by Kalidas Nag and other scholars. It was a political project which aimed to trace India’s influence on the art and culture of other countries outside of the subcontinent. The primary intent of this society was to study and explore the history of ancient India and its connection with Southeast Asian nations like Thailand, Indonesia, and Cambodia.

The first half of the 20th century was a turbulent period in Indian politics. The nationalist movement was in full swing and the Swadeshi movement saw the emergence of a new nationalist spirit. Indians rejected both foreign goods and the English education system. The National Council for Education was established to promote Indian philosophical thought. Bengali intellectuals like Ramananda Chatterjee, editor of *Modern Review*, and Satish Chandra Mukherjee, editor of *Dawn*, directly advocated for Hindu nationalism in the public sphere. A group of young Bengali scholars emerged during this period who introduced a new discourse in the practice of Indian history. Most of them received their higher education degrees from France or the Netherlands. It was by their initiative that the Greater India Society was established. Eminent historians like R C Majumdar and Nag were members of this society, and were heavily influenced by French Indologists. The primary aim of this intellectual movement was to explore India’s historic connections with its neighbouring regions.

What was it that compelled this group to reimagine the history of India? According to scholars Susan Bayly and Phanindranath Bose, the Greater India fraternity rejected

British historiography of ancient India, and their scholarship was marked by strong Islamophobia. Most of them consciously kept silent about the Muslim rulers of India to highlight the ancient glory of the “Indian” (Hindu) civilisation and the expansion of Hindu empires. Muslim rulers were identified as external political forces to introduce a new discourse against the Eurocentric historiography of ancient Indian civilisation and Hindu imperialism.

This new intervention created a unique response in India, especially in the Bengali intellectual sphere. In his lecture on the idea of a “greater India” before he visited Java, Rabindranath Tagore emphasised the construction of the history of the “Hindu colonies” of ancient India. That said, he did not completely ignore the history of India’s Muslim rulers, writing about the Muslim rulers of Bengal in the periodical *Bharati*. Following Tagore’s footsteps, Suniti Kumar Chattopadhyay brought the Greater India thesis into the public sphere. Chattopadhyay wrote about the spread of Hindu culture across the Indian Ocean. In the book *Bharat Sanskriti* (1944), he discussed the inception of the Hindu civilisation, the spread of the Sanskrit language in Asia and the presence of Buddhism in Burma. In particular, he repeatedly referred to Southeast Asian countries as Hindu colonies.

Dinesh Chandra Sen introduced a new discourse—*Brihat Banga* (Greater Bengal)—by reinterpreting the project of imagining a greater India. Like the Greater India Society, he strongly criticised the accounts of Islam and their empires in Indian history. Sen argued that most of India’s history was state history written by Muslims, with stories of victory and defeat, battles and achievements of victorious Muslims. He went beyond the history of wars and conflicts, focusing on the history of cultural development and made a historical inquiry into the rise and development of Bengali from ancient times. Through the Hindu-isation of history with Bengal at the centre, Sen advocated and embraced a narrow provincialism. He aimed to construct a new identity of Bengal and explore the history of Bengali relations with the rest of India but did not find support among his contemporaries.

Nag and Bijan Raj Chatterji of the Greater India Society simultaneously took up a project of writing a new history of Asia. Books like Nag’s *Greater India* (1926) or Chatterji’s *India and Java* (1933) and *Indian Cultural Influence in Cambodia* (1928) evidence the tendency of Bengali historians to

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Indianise Southeast Asia. Similarly, the *Journal of the Greater India Society* played a special role in materialising this pan-Asian imagination and compiling an Indianist history of Southeast Asia.

However, this project of writing India's national history from a Hindu cultural viewpoint gradually lost its relevance in the post-independence period. Historical research began to be influenced by postcolonial and Marxist ideology. The historiography of India gained a new dimension in the narratives of historians like Romila Thapar, Irfan Habib, and D N Jha. Thapar established a more scientific approach to studying history, discarding the nostalgia for a "lost India." Habib explored the history of ancient India challenging monolithic and sectarian perspectives. In his book, *Holy Cow: Beef in Indian Dietary Traditions* (2001), Jha challenged Hindu orthodoxy by outlining the practice of beef-eating as the norm in Vedic and post-Vedic societies.

Though the overtly nationalistic approach and orthodox Hindu bigotry thwarted the Greater India project, it did not stop the process of saffronisation of Indian history. Several attempts continue to be made to erase India's Muslim history—including place names, cultural norms, built heritage—from public memory. From renaming railway stations to claiming important Muslim built heritage as originally

Hindu, it foregrounds the attempts of Hindu ideologues to rewrite Indian history from a narrow, sectarian and communal perspective. Even the recent changes in the National Council of Educational Research and Training history textbooks are part of initiatives to undermine India's diverse and multicultural past. Interestingly, Hindu ideologues often argue that their historiography offers a counter-narrative against the discourse of Western hegemony. But, in reality, their attempts are but a slavish imitation of the Western discourse of historiography in which a distorted history is presented, imitating the idea of European radical nationalism. European colonial historians have, in many cases, provided incomplete information about India's rich ancient history. Similarly, Hindu nationalist historians of India have deliberately sidelined important parts of India's Muslim history, especially in the medieval era. This project of rewriting national history often placates a particular ideology and captures the biased perspective of Hindu nationalists; it is as evident in the historiography of the Greater India Society as it is in the present-day saffronisation of our history.

Pratim Das (pratimdas60@gmail.com) is a PhD scholar in the Department of Comparative Indian Language and Literature, University of Calcutta. His research interests include Indian travel writings, colonial migration, labour history and movement, and partition.

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